

Standard solutions of iron(III), bismuth(III) and thorium(IV) were prepared from ferric alum, bismuth nitrate and thorium nitrate respectively using AnalaR chemicals. The metal contents were determined by standard methods.

Standard EDTA solution was prepared from S. Merck's reagent grade Titriplex III. The solution was standardised against zinc solution using Erio T as indicator. This solution was diluted to obtain 0.01M solution of EDTA.

For the titration of iron(III) with EDTA, a 1% ethanolic solution of ASPHA was prepared. The iron-ASPHA complex (0.005M) was prepared by mixing 10 ml 0.05M ferric alum solution and 10 ml 0.01M ASPHA solution in ethanol, diluted to 100 ml with ethanol and used as indicator for the determination of bismuth and thorium.

Subtract the blank titre from the original titres. Typical results of titrations are given in Table 1.

Interferences :

The interferences of various ions are almost the same for Fe(III), Bi(III), and Th(IV) determinations since the titrations are performed in media of nearly the same pH range. Ions such as Ce(IV), Ti(IV), V(V), Nb(V) and Mo(VI) were eliminated prior to the titration by repeated extraction with a chloroform solution ($0.25\frac{W}{V}$) of ASPHA from 5M hydrochloric acid media. Alkaline earth metals and Al(III) were tolerated up to about 20-times excess, whereas Mg(II), Pb(II), Sb(III) and As(III) were tolerated only up to 10-times excess. Zn(II), Mn(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) could be tolerated up to 5-times and Cu(II) interfered even in small amounts. Sn(II), Ta(V) and W(VI) interfered seriously.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF IRON, BISMUTH and THORIUM

Iron taken (mg)	Iron found* (mg)	Standard Deviation	Bismuth taken (mg)	Bismuth found* (mg)	Standard Deviation	Thorium taken (mg)	Thorium found* (mg)	Standard Deviation
5.00	4.99	0.0014	5.43	5.43	0.0021	5.45	5.44	0.0012
10.00	10.02	0.0017	10.86	10.85	0.0018	10.91	10.90	0.0016
20.00	20.04	0.0016	21.73	21.77	0.0022	21.82	21.85	0.0018

* Average of six experiments

Procedure for Iron :

Take an aliquot of iron(III) solution containing about 10 mg of the metal and add enough 0.1N sodium hydroxide solution to give a faint turbidity. Add 12.5 ml of 0.2M potassium chloride and 5.1 ml of 0.2M hydrochloric acid. Dilute to 50 ml and adjust pH in the range 1.0-2.2 using hydrochloric acid or alkali. Add 1 ml of ASPHA solution and titrate against 0.01M EDTA. At the end point the colour of the solution changes from reddish violet to faint yellow.

Procedure for Bismuth or Thorium :

Measure out a suitable aliquot of bismuth or thorium solution and dilute the solution to 50 ml after adding 12.5 ml of 0.2M potassium chloride and 5.1 ml 0.2M hydrochloric acid. Adjust the pH in the range 0.7-2.3 for bismuth and 1.5-2.5 for thorium. Add 0.5 ml of iron-ASPHA complex and titrate slowly against EDTA. At the end point the reddish violet colour sharply changes to colourless.

In the titration of bismuth and thorium in which iron-ASPHA complex is the indicator, conduct a blank titration without the respective metal ions, keeping all the other components a constant.

Complexing anions like fluoride, oxalate, phosphate, and tartrate were tolerated only in small amounts.

References

1. V. R. M. KAIMAL and S. C. SHOME, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962, **27**, 594.
2. H. R. DAS and S. C. SHOME, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1966, **35**, 256.
3. B. DAS and S. C. SHOME, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1968, **43**, 140.
4. C. P. SAVARIAR and JOY JOSEPH, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1969, **47**, 347.
5. C. P. SAVARIAR and JOY JOSEPH, *Talanta*, 1970, **17**, 45.
6. C. P. SAVARIAR and JOY JOSEPH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 15.

A Study of Interference of Cu(II) in Determination of Bismuth with Potassium Hexathiocyanato Chromate(III)*

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ROESLER¹ prepared $M_3Cr(SCN)_6 \cdot xH_2O$ from chrome alum and alkali thiocyanates. Dubskey and Wangenhofer² obtained $K_3Cr(SCN)_6 \cdot 4H_2O$ as

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dark violet cubic crystals and $[\text{NH}_4]_3 \text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as pale violet cubic crystals. Tsamadou⁹ synthesised chromium thiocyanate complexes of Sn, As and Cd. Lewis⁴ and his co-workers analysed the type of bonding in metal thiocyanates by vibrational spectra. In the present communication an attempt has been made to study the cause of interference of Cu(II) in the determination of Bi(III) with potassium hexathiocyanato chromate(III).

Experimental

Pure or A.R. S.M./B.D.H. quality chemicals were used.

Compound 1—Potassium hexathiocyanato chromate(III) was prepared and standardised by methods adopted by Roesler¹ and Bjerrum⁶.

Compound 2—Bismuth hexathiocyanato chromate(III): To a cold $\text{Bi}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution (M/10) in 2N HNO_3 , a freshly prepared solution of potassium hexathiocyanato chromate(III) (M/10) was added dropwise when a shining red compound separates out slowly. It was filtered, washed with water and dried in air. [Found: Bi, 34.21; Cr, 8.50; and SCN, 57.20%. $\text{BiCr}(\text{SCN})_6$ requires Bi, 34.32; Cr, 8.54 and SCN, 57.14%]. It is practically insoluble in water, alcohol, CCl_4 , ether, acetone and dil. mineral acids. But it is soluble in saturated sodium thiosulphate solution, alkalies and basic organic solvents.

Compound 3—To a mixture of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (M/10) and $\text{Bi}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (M/10) in water containing 2N HNO_3 , an aqueous solution of potassium hexathiocyanato chromate(III) (M/10) was added dropwise until present in slight excess indicated by the reddish-violet colour of the supernatant liquid. After some time a brown-black compound separates out. It was washed with water and dried in air. It is practically insoluble in water, alcohol, CCl_4 , benzene and acetone. But it is soluble in strong mineral acids, saturated sodium thiosulphate solution and alkalies. [Found: Bi, 20.18; Cr, 10.03; Cu, 5.9 and SCN, 61.60%. $\text{Bi}[\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6]\text{Cu}[\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ requires Bi, 20.22; Cr, 10.06; Cu, 6.14 and SCN, 61.76%].

Results and Discussion

Several workers⁶⁻¹⁰ have pointed out that SCN^- may coordinate to the metal atom of a complex through either the sulphur or the nitrogen atom. Therefore three kinds of SCN^- complexes are possible, e.g., M-SCN thiocyanate, M-NCS isothiocyanate and M-SCN-M bridged SCN complexes. The infrared spectra of SCN^- and its metal complexes have two characteristic bands, one band of $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching vibration near 2050 cm^{-1} and the other band of S-C stretching vibration at 750 cm^{-1} . According to Lewis⁴ and his coworkers in the assignment of the lowest frequency to the bonding

mode the possibility in same region ($500-400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) has to be considered. Preliminary X-ray results¹¹ have taken to indicate sulphur bonding for Cr(III) hexathiocyanate. Furthermore, sulphur bonding for Cr(III) is against chemical evidence. Seel¹² concluded that nitrogen bonding existed in $\text{K}_3\text{Cr}(\text{CNS})_6$. The frequencies reported for $\text{K}_3\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (isothiocyanate) are

2105 cm^{-1} s $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching (NCS antisymmetric),
 820 cm^{-1} vw C-S stretching (NCS symmetric),
 470 cm^{-1} m NCS bending and 961 cm^{-1} wm overtone.

In thiocyanate complexes the C-S bond becomes weaker than in SCN^- , while the strength of $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ bond increases. In isothiocyanate complexes the strength of C-S bond increases while that of $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ bond remains almost unchanged¹³. In the infrared spectrum of compound 1 a sharp band at 2060 cm^{-1} is due to $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching, the two medium intensity bands at 345 cm^{-1} and 475 cm^{-1} indicate probably metal-nitrogen bond and NCS bending. The disappearance of $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching at 2060 cm^{-1} is very abnormal in the compound. In the compound 3 the two medium intensity bands at 350 cm^{-1} and 460 cm^{-1} appear respectively at a higher and at a lower frequency in comparison to the bands observed for the compound 1. The $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching frequency appears at 2090 cm^{-1} in the compound 3.

The Laporte-forbidden d-d absorption spectra of Cr(III) with many ligands have been interpreted by Ligand Field Theory. In the electronic spectra of Cr(III) complexes three spin-allowed transitions are expected¹⁴. In the $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ complex the bands are found at

17400 cm^{-1} ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} - {}^4\text{T}_{2g}$ transition at $574.7 \text{ m}\mu$
 24700 cm^{-1} ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} - {}^4\text{T}_{1g}$ (F) transition at $404 \text{ m}\mu$
 37300 cm^{-1} ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} - {}^4\text{T}_{1g}$ (P) transition at $270 \text{ m}\mu$

Since d-orbital splitting ability of NCS^- is more than water we expect the d-d band at a higher energy level. In case of hexathiocyanato chromate(III) only the first two spin-allowed bands at $570 \text{ m}\mu$ and $420 \text{ m}\mu$ have been observed. These have been assigned to the ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} - {}^4\text{T}_{2g}$ and ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} - {}^4\text{T}_{1g}$ (F) transitions respectively. The third spin-allowed band of Cr(III) complex corresponding to the transition ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} - {}^4\text{T}_{1g}$ (P) could not be observed in our $380-620 \text{ m}\mu$ range spectrum. The potassium hexathiocyanato chromate(III) dissociates slowly in presence of light and at a higher or lower pH than that of neutral solution. In presence of 2N HNO_3 there is a quick exchange of H_2O and SCN^- in the octahedral coordination sphere of Cr. A slight variation was observed in the electronic spectrum of potassium hexathiocyanato chromate(III) which was exposed to light for some hours.

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Synthesis of γ -(5-Arylhydantoin-5)-Butyric Acids**

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References

- ROESLER, *Annalen*, 1867, **141**, 185.
- J. V. DUBSKY and E. WANGENHOFER, *Chem. Obzor.*, 1940, **15**, 217; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1941, **1**, 3199.
- D. TSAMADOS, *Priktika* (Akad. Athenon), 1930, **5**, 61; cf. *Chem. Abs.*, **26**, 3451.
- J. LEWIS, R. S. NYHOLM and P. W. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4590;
(a) O. PRECILE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**(2), 210.
- N. BJERRUM, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1921, **118**, 131.
- F. BASOLO, W. H. BADDELY and J. L. BURMISTER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 12.
- I. LINDQUIST and B. STRANDBERG, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1957, **10**, 176.
- P. C. H. MITCHELL and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1912.
- R. G. PEARSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 3533.
- M. TRAMER, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1960, **16**, 505.
- ZVONKOVA, *Zhur. fiz. Khim.*, 1957, **31**, 2174.
- SEEL, Coordination Chem. Conference, Copenhagen, 1953, p. 46; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1956, **283**, 351.
- D. FORSTER, W. HORROCKS and W. DE JR., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 339.
- R. TSUCHIDA, M. KOBAYASHI and K. NAKAMURA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1936, **11**, 38.

It has been reported¹ that β -(5-arylhydantoin-5)-propionic acids showed antitubercular activity. This prompted us to prepare the next higher homologue, viz. hydantoin derivatives of γ -arylbutyric acids for pharmacological screening. Our earlier attempts² to prepare β -aryl- γ -(5-arylhydantoin-5)-butyric acids from β -aryl- γ -arylbutyric acids by Bucherer-Berg reaction failed due to steric hindrance of bulky β -aromatic group in butyric acids. Hence, an attempt was made to prepare γ -(5-arylhydantoin-5)-butyric acids from γ -arylbutyric acids, which were readily converted into hydantoin derivatives by Bucherer reaction.

The γ -arylbutyric acids have been prepared by Friedel-Crafts reaction between substituted benzene derivatives(I) and glutaric anhydride (Fig. 1) by

Fig. 1

TABLE-1
 γ -(SUBSTITUTED AROYL)BUTYRIC ACIDS(II) AND
 γ -[5-(SUBSTITUTED ARYL)HYDANTOIN-5]-BUTYRIC ACIDS(III)

No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	II			III			Procedure	
				mp/bp °C	Yield %	Procedure	m.p. °C	Yield %	Found N %		Reqd. N %
1	H	H	H	132	60	A	177.5	55	10.54	10.68	C
2	CH ₃	H	H	—	—	—	133.0	—	10.83	10.15	—
3	H	H	4-CH ₃	148	40	A	185.0	60	10.04	10.14	C
4	CH ₃	H	4-CH ₃	—	—	—	178.0	—	9.42	9.65	—
5	H	H	4-OCH ₃	138	61	B	180.0	60	10.15	9.59	C
6	CH ₃	H	4-OCH ₃	—	—	—	151.5	—	9.07	9.15	—
7	H	H	4-Cl	121	65	A	210.0	65	9.70	9.45	C
8	CH ₃	H	4-Cl	35	—	—	184.0	—	9.88	9.32	—
9	H	H	4-C ₂ H ₅	98	50	B	175.0	44	10.24	9.66	C
10	CH ₃	H	4-C ₂ H ₅	40	—	—	184.5	—	9.36	9.21	—
11	H	3-CH ₃	4-OCH ₃	139	71	B	234.0	90	9.25	9.15	D
12	CH ₃	3-CH ₃	4-OCH ₃	—	—	—	183.0	—	9.60	8.70	—
13	H	3-Cl	4-OCH ₃	156	80.3	B	215.0	70	9.27	8.58	D
14	CH ₃	3-Cl	4-OCH ₃	76	—	—	185.0	—	8.29	8.22	—
15	H	3-OCH ₃	4-OCH ₃	142	41	B	227.5	74	9.01	8.69	D
16	CH ₃	3-OCH ₃	4-OCH ₃	—	—	—	204.0	—	8.64	8.34	—
17	H	2-CH ₃	4-OCH ₃	121	70	B	—	—	—	—	—
18	H	2-Cl	5-OCH ₃	105	61	B	—	—	—	—	—
19	CH ₃	2-Cl	5-OCH ₃	190/1mm (bath)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
20	H	2-Cl	4-OCH ₃	114-6	48	B	Did not form hydantoin derivative				—
21	CH ₃	2-Cl	4-OCH ₃	200/1mm (bath)	—	—					—
22	H	2-OCH ₃	4-OCH ₃	—	—	B	—	—	—	—	—
23	H	2-OCH ₃	5-OCH ₃	—	—	B	—	—	—	—	—

- Remarks : 1. All m.p./b.p. are uncorrected.
2. All the compounds have given satisfactory carbon, hydrogen and chlorine analyses wherever required.
3. Molecular weights of all the compounds were confirmed by mass spectrometry.